

Temporal snapshot of parasitoid wasp communities on three flowering plant species and implications for the rosy apple aphid regulation (*Dysaphis plantaginea*) in apple orchards.

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Running title: Forbs structure parasitoid communities in orchards

Key message:

- Plant species associated with apple trees structured parasitoid wasp communities.
- Parasitoid abundances were twice higher on *V. persica* and *V. sativa* than on *C. bursa-pastoris* plants.
- 6% of the parasitoid wasps collected on flowers were rosy apple aphid parasitoids.
- Aphid parasitism was 2.7 times higher on apple trees associated with *V. persica* than on control trees without vegetation.

Abstract: Parasitoid wasps contribute to biological control services. Parasitoid adults are highly dependent on sugar-rich resources. Adding flowering plants providing nectar in crop fields promotes parasitoid wasps, but not always pest parasitism because addition of flowering plants may attract parasitoid species that are not directly involved in the control of crop pests. In a factorial experiment conducted for one year in pesticide-free orchards, we analysed the effects of three common plant species (*Capsella bursa-pastoris* Medik., *Veronica persica* Poir. and *Vicia sativa* L.) in association with apple trees on parasitoid wasp recruitment and parasitism of one major apple pest, *Dysaphis plantaginea* (Passerini). We combined morphological and molecular identifications to characterise the parasitoid communities associated with each plant species. Parasitoid communities were different between plant species. Plant effects on the abundance of the parasitoid wasps did not depend on the amount of floral resources provided by the tested plants. Over the whole season, the parasitoid wasp species *Ephedrus persicae* (Froggatt) and *Aphidius matricariae* (Haliday) involved in *D. plantaginea* parasitism accounted for 6% of the total parasitoid abundance and were mainly associated with *V. persica* plots. We observed a higher parasitism rate in apple trees associated with *V. persica* and a lower number of aphid colonies in apple trees associated with *V. sativa*. However, plant treatments had no effect on the abundance of *D. plantaginea* or on generalist predator and ant occurrences in aphid colonies. As a result, the three plant tested had a limited impact on the rosy apple aphid regulation overall.

Keywords: Conservation biological control; barcoding; parasitism; floral resources; *Aphidius matricariae*; *Ephedrus persicae*.

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Communautés des hyménoptères parasitoïdes sur trois espèces de plantes à fleurs et implications pour la régulation du puceron cendré (*Dysaphis plantaginea*) dans les vergers de pommiers.

Résumé : Les hyménoptères parasitoïdes contribuent à la régulation des insectes ravageurs mais dépendent souvent de ressources florales riches en nectar pour se reproduire et se développer. L'ajout de plantes à fleurs dans les cultures permet d'accroître les populations d'hyménoptères parasitoïdes, mais ne favorise pas toujours le parasitisme des ravageurs, les plantes à fleurs pouvant attirer des espèces de parasitoïdes qui ne sont pas directement impliquées dans le contrôle des ravageurs. Dans le cadre d'une expérimentation factorielle menée pendant une année dans des vergers sans pesticides, nous avons analysé les effets de trois espèces végétales communes (*Capsella bursa-pastoris* Medik., *Veronica persica* Poir. et *Vicia sativa* L.) en association aux pommiers sur le recrutement des parasitoïdes et le parasitisme d'un ravageur majeur, le puceron cendré, *Dysaphis plantaginea* (Passerini). Les identifications morphologiques et moléculaires des espèces de parasitoïdes ont permis la caractérisation des communautés associées à chaque espèce végétale. Les communautés de parasitoïdes étaient différentes d'une espèce végétale à l'autre. Les effets des plantes sur l'abondance des parasitoïdes ne dépendaient pas de la quantité de ressources florales des plantes testées. Sur l'ensemble de la saison, deux espèces parasitant *D. plantaginea* ont été observées : *Ephedrus persicae* (Froggatt) et *Aphidius matricariae* (Haliday). Ces deux espèces représentaient 6% de l'abondance totale des parasitoïdes. Elles ont été principalement observées dans les fleurs de *V. persica*. Le parasitisme des pucerons étaient plus élevés dans les pommiers associés à *V. persica* et un nombre plus faible de colonies de pucerons dans les pommiers associés à *V. sativa*. Les trois plantes testées n'avaient toutefois pas d'effet sur les abondances totales de pucerons dans les pommiers, ni sur les prédateurs généralistes et sur les fourmis observés dans les colonies de pucerons. Leurs impacts sur la régulation du puceron cendré du pommier restaient globalement limités.

1. Introduction

Parasitoid wasps play a critical role in agroecosystems as natural enemies of pest insects and thus, contribute to biological control services. Adult parasitoid wasps feed mainly on sugar-rich resources such as floral nectar or honeydew (Lu et al., 2014; Luquet et al., 2021), and access to floral nectar positively affects their longevity (Russell, 2015). Nectar consumption also improves the fecundity of synovigenic parasitoids that mature eggs throughout their adult life (Benelli et al., 2017). Adequate and sufficient food sources are thus needed to increase the longevity and fecundity of parasitoid wasps. Adding plants providing floral nectar (*e.g.* flower strips, companion plants or cover crops) within or around crop fields is a potential strategy to promote parasitoid wasps and strengthen biological control service (Shields et al., 2019). This approach also benefits other groups of natural enemies such as hoverflies, lacewings or ladybugs (Boetzi et al., 2021; Haaland et al., 2011).

In recent years, using local and spontaneous flowering plant species has gained attention to promote biological control (Fiedler et al., 2008; Fourain, 2022; Zaviezo & Muñoz, 2023; Laffon et al., 2024). Common wild flowering plants are well adapted to local conditions and can be highly effective to favour beneficial insects (Balfour & Ratnieks, 2022; Blaix et al., 2018; Wignall et al., 2023). Several studies have been conducted to evaluate the attractiveness of local wild flowering plants for natural enemies (*e.g.* Denis et al., 2021; Gibson et al., 2019; Lundin et al., 2019; Retallack et al., 2019), but cascading effects on insect pests and associated damage need to be better explored (Zaviezo & Muñoz, 2023). It is not always clear whether flowering plants attract parasitoid species that are involved in insect pest regulation. Parasitoid wasps visiting flowers are usually not identified at species level (*e.g.* Saunders & Luck, 2018; Aparicio et al., 2021; Mateos-Fierro et al., 2021). Accurate identification of parasitoid species is essential to establish links between flowers and insect pest regulation, but remains challenging because of their high diversity and the lack of taxonomic expertise (Forbes et al., 2018; Miller et al., 2021; Polaszek & Vilhemsen, 2023). The identification of parasitoid wasps collected from flowers may be facilitated by the use of molecular tools such as barcoding

(Hebert et al., 2003). Barcoding methods have been used to study interactions between parasitoid wasps and their hosts (Miller et al., 2021), but less commonly to describe communities of parasitoid wasps visiting flowers (but see González et al., 2022).

Here, we studied the parasitoid communities in apple orchards. There are numerous pests in apple orchards, resulting in a high frequency of pesticide treatments (Desprat et al., 2021). The rosy apple aphid (RAA), *Dysaphis plantaginea* Passerini (Hemiptera: Aphididae), is one of the major apple pests, causing curled leaves and distorted apples, and thus economic losses in apple production (Blommers et al., 2004). Generalist predators such as hoverflies, ladybirds, spiders, bugs or earwigs are key RAA natural enemies (Dib et al., 2010; Lefebvre et al., 2017; Porcel et al., 2018; Rodríguez-Gasol et al., 2019). In addition, several Aphidiinae (Hymenoptera: Braconidae) species belonging to *Ephedrus* Haliday and *Aphidius* Nees genera are common RAA parasitoids. *Ephedrus persicae* Froggatt was the dominant species reported in several European studies (Bribosia et al., 2005; Dib et al., 2010; Peusens et al., 2006), but Rodríguez-Gasol et al. (2019) observed in Spain that more than 90% of the parasitoids identified in RAA colonies were *Aphidius* spp., mainly *Aphidius matricariae* Haliday. Other parasitoid species, belonging to the genera *Lysiphlebus* Förster, *Binodoxys* Mackauer or *Trioxys* Haliday, may also attack RAA, but are less common (Dib et al. 2010; Turpeau et al., 2020). Parasitism levels in RAA colonies are generally low (Dib et al., 2010a, Dib et al., 2010b, Albert et al, 2017, Howard et al., 2024). By providing additional sources of sugar to adult parasitoids, the addition of flowering plants may promote RAA parasitoids and increase RAA parasitism (Rodríguez-Gasol et al., 2019; Tougeron et al., 2023), but the flower preferences of RAA parasitoids remain poorly understood.

The overall aim of this study was to determine whether common wild flowering plant species can attract and promote natural enemies involved in RAA regulation, with particular emphasis on communities of parasitoid wasps. We hypothesised that the plant species attracting the highest number of RAA parasitoids also enhance RAA parasitism rates in apple trees.

2. Material and methods

2.1. Experimental apple orchards

The study was conducted in 2022 in two apple orchards at INRAE research station in Avignon, south-eastern France (Fig. 1). The orchards were located in a peri-urban area surrounded by other experimental orchards, in particular peach trees, and bordered by a hedgerow at the northern edge. The two apple orchards were 250 m apart and were pesticide-free for over ten years. The first orchard (0.2 ha) was planted in 2004 and had six rows of apple trees (Ariane variety). The second orchard (0.2 ha) was planted in 2010 and had ten rows of apple trees (Gala and Granny Smith, five rows for each variety). The three apple tree varieties have similar phenologies, flowering in mid-April. Sprinkler systems were placed in the tree rows and irrigated both the trees and the flowering plants. Inter-row vegetation and field edges were mown once a month to prevent non-sown plants from flowering.

2.2. Experimental design

Three flowering plant species - *Capsella bursa-pastoris* Medik. (Brassicaceae), *Veronica persica* Poir. (Plantaginaceae) and *Vicia sativa* L. (Fabaceae) - were tested as different plant treatments using bare soil as comparison in a completely randomised block design (Fig. 1). These three plant species are commonly observed in apple orchards of the study area (Laffon et al., 2024). They start blooming before mid-May (*i.e.* when the RAA infestation is at its peak) and are known to be visited by several taxa of parasitoid wasps, including Braconidae (Araj & Wratten, 2015; Dib et al., 2012; Gardarin et al., 2021). Eight blocks were established to account for spatial heterogeneity in the apple orchards, including apple varieties and distances to hedgerows (Fig. 1). Within each block, eight apple trees with homogeneous trunk circumferences were selected to limit vigour heterogeneity between the apple trees. Blocks were separated by at least 8 m in each orchard. Plant treatments were randomised within blocks. Flower and bare soil plots were located in the tree row and corresponded to two consecutive apple trees surrounded by each of the three plant species or by bare soil (2.5m x 1m). Within each plot, the distance between trees was 1.5 m. In total, there were 32 plots including 64 monitored apple trees.

The seeds of the three tested plant species were supplied by a seed company in south-eastern France and labelled “végétal local” allowing the use of local plant provenance (Phytosem, Gap, France). They were sown in October 2021 in the row under the apple tree (sowing density: 2.4g/m² for *V. persica* and *C. bursa-pastoris* and 4.5g/m² for *V. sativa*). Germination was visually monitored at regular intervals until February 2022. Since poor emergence resulted in unoccupied gaps, particularly in *C. bursa-pastoris* plots, seedlings were additionally grown in a greenhouse in February 2022 and transplanted into these gaps in early March 2022. All seedlings were manually watered and monitored daily for the first three weeks to obtain sufficient establishment. Weeds were removed within each plot every week throughout the study period.

2.4 Field sampling

All plots were sampled fortnightly from April to June 2022.

2.4.1 Sampling in the flowering plant plots

At each sampling date, the total number of flowers or inflorescences per m² was counted in each plot. Counts included individual flowers of *V. persica* and *V. sativa* and the number of inflorescences of *C. bursa-pastoris* since the later species has very small flowers that are difficult to count. The term floral unit hereafter refers to a *C. bursa-pastoris* inflorescences and individual flowers of the two other species. The numbers of active extrafloral nectaries per m² were additionally recorded in *V. sativa* plots.

The overall abundances of arthropods visiting flowers at each plot were recorded to account for potential competition with the parasitoid wasps for floral resources (Campbell et al., 2012). Plots were randomly visited at each sampling date. Arthropods visiting flowers were counted for five minutes in each plot in avoiding disturbance (slow movements). We considered butterflies (Lepidoptera), bees and wasps (Hymenoptera: Apoidea), hoverflies (Diptera: Syrphidae), other flies (Diptera), ladybirds (Coleoptera: Coccinellidae), other beetles (Coleoptera) and spiders (Aranea). Following careful

observation, parasitoid wasps were collected using a sweep net (four sweeps per plot). Parasitoids were kept in 8 mL tubes with 70% ethanol prior to further identification. All observations and net samples were taken between 9:00 am and 2:00 pm during sunny or slightly cloudy days with a temperature above 15°C and a low wind speed (Beaufort Wind Scale <3).

2.4.2 Sampling on apple trees associated with the flowering plant plots

First, RAA infestation was recorded at each sampling date by counting both the number of RAA colonies and the number of RAA in at least one colony in each apple tree of the monitored plot. RAA were counted in randomly marked colonies selected at the first sampling date. Average values of the number of colonies per tree were calculated on the two apple trees per plot. We multiplied the number of RAA per colony (average per plot) by the number of RAA colonies per tree (average per plot) to estimate the average number of RAA per tree and sampling date in each monitored plot (hereafter, named RAA abundance).

Second, the abundances of generalist predators and mummies were estimated at each sampling date in all the RAA colonies (marked and unmarked) observed in each apple tree of the monitored plot. Earwig adults and larvae (Dermaptera: Forficulidae), hoverfly larvae (Diptera: Syrphidae), ladybug adults and larvae (Coleoptera: Coccinellidae), spiders (Araneae) were added to estimate the abundance of generalist predators (average tree values/date/plot). Similarly, mummies were added to estimates RAA mummies. The parasitism rate was calculated as a ratio of the number of RAA mummies divided by the total number of parasitized and non-parasitized RAA (average tree values/date/plot). We also recorded the presence and absence of ants (Hymenoptera: Formicidae) in RAA colonies to estimate ant occurrence in each plot.

Finally, the proportion of apples presenting aphid damage was measured at the end of June. We counted the number of distorted apples and the total number of apples on each tree of the monitored plots.

2.5. Parasitoid identification

Parasitoid species involved in the regulation of *D. plantaginea* were identified in three steps. First, parasitoid wasps collected by netting in each flower plot were sorted in the laboratory and identified to family level (Delvard, 2020; Goulet et al., 1993). Then, morphological and molecular identification were combined to identify more precisely Braconidae species. A non-destructive Chelex®100 (Biorad) DNA was carried out in order to allow for a morphological re-examination of the Braconidae specimen after the sequencing. PCR amplifications were performed with the *LepF1/LepR1* primers targeting a specific fragment of the cytochrome c oxidase subunit 1 gene (*COI*, 658 bp), using a Mastercycler thermocycler (Eppendorf). The reaction mixture included in 30 µL PCR reaction volume containing 1X Flexi® buffer, 1U of Taq polymerase, 200 µM of each dNTP, 2 mM MgCl₂, 100µg/mL BSA, 0.4 µM of each primer, and 3 µL of DNA template. PCR conditions starts with an initial denaturation step of 3 min at 95 °C followed by 35 cycles 30 s at 95°C, 45 s of annealing at 56°C, and 1 min of elongation at 72 °C. The amplification products were sequenced using the Sanger method at Eurofins MWG Operon. The sequences obtained were manually checked and assembled using BioEdit sequence alignment software (Hall, 2011) and then compared to published sequences in the Barcode Of Life Data (BOLD) System V4 database (Ratnasingham & Hebert, 2007). Molecular identifications were considered as valid at genus or species level when similarities of the DNA sequences with BOLD references were higher than 98%. Below this threshold the specimens were considered unidentified. Finally, the molecular identification of the *Aphidius* specimens was cross-checked by morphological identification. We considered all the parasitoids identified as *Aphidius matricariae* and *Ephedrus persicae* as involved in RAA parasitism (Bribosia et al., 2005; Dib et al., 2010; Peusens et al., 2006; Turpeau et al., 2020).

2.6. Statistical analysis

All analyses were conducted using R (R Core, 2023) version 4.2.0. We evaluated differences in floral unit abundance between the three flowering plant treatments per plot and sampling date using

Kruskal–Wallis rank tests followed by Dunn’s test for multiple comparisons (R package: *PMCMRplus*, Pohlert, 2020) and we calculated Spearman correlations between all the variables examined to avoid over-parameterising our models afterwards (Fig. S1).

Generalised linear mixed models (GLMM) (R package: *lme4*, Bates et al., 2015) were used to analyse the effect of plant treatment (tested plants and bare soil) at the plot level for the five sampling dates on the abundance of arthropods, the abundance of parasitoid wasps, the average number of RAA colonies and RAA abundance in apple tree, the average abundance of generalist predators, the presence/absence of ants and the average parasitism rate in RAA colonies. In all GLMMs, plant treatment was considered as a fixed factor. Sampling date and block were included as random factors to account for spatial and temporal autocorrelation. Abundances were tested using Poisson distribution and log-link function. In case of over-dispersion, a negative binomial distribution (log-link function) was applied. Proportion of RAA distorted apples (number of undamaged apples per tree, number of distorted apples per tree) and RAA parasitism rate (number of mummies per tree, number of non-parasitized RAA per tree), were evaluated using the ‘*cbind*’ function (number of mummies per tree, number of non-parasitized RAA per tree), assuming a binomial error distribution with logit-link function. Similarly, ant occurrence was modelled using a binomial error distribution. For response variables measured in flower plots (*i.e.* total abundance of arthropods and abundance of parasitoid wasps), GLMMs included the number of floral units as a covariate, to account for possible density-dependence effects. For *V. sativa*, the number of individual flowers and the number of extrafloral nectaries were highly correlated ($\rho = 0.85$; $p < 0.001$). We therefore used the number of floral units as an indicator of available floral resources. For response variables recorded in apple trees (*i.e.* number of generalist predators, occurrence of ants and parasitism rate per apple tree), GLMMs included the estimated number of RAA per tree as a covariate. Both covariates (floral units and RAA number) were scale-transformed. Model assumptions were checked graphically (R package: *DHARMA*, Hartig, 2022). Type II tests were performed for each model, followed by multiple comparisons using Tukey HSD test (R package: *multcomp*, function *glht*, Hothorn et al., 2008).

The composition of parasitoid communities was assessed at family level and at genus level for Braconidae. The abundances of each parasitoid wasp taxon per plot were added over the whole season. To visualise differences in parasitoid community composition among the three tested plants, we used non-metric multidimensional scaling (NMDS) based on Bray-Curtis dissimilarity. Differences in parasitoid communities were then tested using an Analysis of Similarity (ANOSIM) with 9999 permutations (R package: *vegan*, Oksanen et al., 2013). Finally, we conducted a multilevel analysis with 9999 permutations (R package: *indicspecies*, function: *multpatt*, De Cáceres and Legendre 2009) to identify parasitoid taxa that were significantly associated with plant treatments ($p < 0.05$). The multilevel analysis was applied to parasitoid wasp abundances recorded per plot and sampling date, and to cumulative abundances over the whole season in each plot.

3. Results

3.1. Flower and arthropod abundances on flower plots

The number of floral units was on average 36.8/m²/date (± 5.9) for *C. bursa-pastoris*, 73.8/m²/date (± 12.3) for *V. persica* and 82.9/m²/date (± 16.7) for *V. sativa* plots. No flower occurred in the bare soil plots. Flowering peaks of *V. sativa* and *V. persica* were observed in late April at the second sampling date, while the flowering peak of *C. bursa-pastoris* occurred in early May at the third sampling date (Fig. 2A). The number of floral units differed significantly between plant treatments. We recorded a higher number of floral units in *V. sativa* plots than in *C. bursa-pastoris* plots at the first ($H = 16.98$, $df = 2$, $p < 0.001$) and the second sampling dates ($H = 10.46$, $df = 2$, $p = 0.005$). The number of floral units was lower in *V. sativa* plots than in *V. persica* and *C. bursa-pastoris* plots at the fourth sampling date ($H = 15.69$, $df = 2$, $p < 0.001$). Finally, at the last sampling date, the number of floral units was higher in *C. bursa-pastoris* plots than in *V. persica* and *V. sativa* plots ($H = 20.13$, $df = 2$, $p < 0.001$).

Over the whole season, we recorded 494 arthropods (including 148 parasitoid wasps) by visual observations. The total number of arthropods was significantly influenced by the plant treatment

(Table 1). Higher numbers of arthropods were observed in the three flowering plant species plots than in bare soil plots (10 times higher in *V. sativa* plots, 6 times higher in *V. persica* plots and 3 times higher in *C. bursa-pastoris* plots, Fig. 2B). Higher numbers of arthropods were also recorded in *V. sativa* and *V. persica* plots than in *C. bursa-pastoris* plots and in *V. sativa* plots than in *V. persica* plots (Fig. 2B). These differences were significant with and without correcting by the number of floral units (Fig. S2 and Table 1 and S2).

3.2. Parasitoid wasp communities

Over the whole season, we collected 315 parasitoid wasps with on average 0.22 (± 0.11) individuals in the bare soil plots, 1.46 (± 0.38) in *C. bursa-pastoris* plots, 3.05 (± 0.41) individuals in *V. persica* plots and 3.2 (± 0.70) individuals in *V. sativa* plots. The total number of parasitoid wasps was significantly influenced by the treatment (Table 1). Higher numbers of parasitoid wasps were collected in the three plant species plots than in bare soil plots (14 times higher on *V. sativa* plots, 13 times higher on *V. persica* plots and 6 times higher on *C. bursa-pastoris* plots, Fig. 2C). We also collected significantly more parasitoid wasps in *V. persica* and *V. sativa* plots than in *C. bursa-pastoris* plots ($p = 0.019$ and $p = 0.022$). Again, these differences were significant with and without correcting by the number of floral units (Fig. S2 and Table 1 and S2).

The 315 parasitoid wasps belonged to 16 families, 51 genera and 30 species (Table S3). Braconidae was the most abundant family in all plant treatments and accounted for 48% of the total abundance (Fig. 3A). The NMDS ordination suggested differences in the parasitoid wasp communities at the family level between plant treatments (Fig. 3B), which was confirmed by the corresponding ANOSIM test ($R = 0.18$, $p = 0.009$). Multilevel pattern analysis showed that Ichneumonidae and Pteromalidae were significantly associated with *V. persica* and *V. sativa* plots ($p = 0.010$ and $p = 0.040$; Fig. 3A and Table S1).

Full *COI* barcodes were amplified for 147 Braconidae adults (96 % of the total), among which 123 were assigned to 15 genera (Fig. 3C). Among them, *Aphidius*, *Dacnusa* and *Chorebus* were the most abundant genera, accounting for 34%, 13% and 9% of the total Braconidae abundance (Fig. 3C). ANOSIM test showed a significant difference in the Braconidae communities at genus level among the plant treatments ($R = 0.30$, $p < 0.001$; Fig. 3D). *Aphidius* was identified as significantly associated with *V. persica* and *C. bursa-pastoris* plots ($p = 0.009$) and *Chorebus* was identified as an indicator of *V. sativa* plots ($p = 0.003$).

Nine *Aphidius* species were finally identified, of which *A. matricariae* and *A. rhopalosiphi* were the most abundant parasitoid wasps (Fig. 4A). *Ephedrus persicae* and *A. matricariae* were the only collected parasitizing RAA (Bribosia et al., 2005; Dib et al., 2010; Peusens et al., 2006; Turpeau et al., 2020). *Ephedrus persicae* and *A. matricariae* accounted for 6% of the total abundance of parasitoid wasps (2 and 17 individuals, respectively). 57% of these RAA parasitoid wasps (11/19) were observed in *V. persica* plots (Fig. 4B).

3.3. Aphid infestation, parasitism and generalist predators in apple trees

We counted 1.2 (± 2.3) RAA colonies per tree and sampling date. We estimated an average number of 32.9 (± 6.7) RAA per colony and sampling date and a total of 92.7 (± 20.8) RAA per tree and sampling date. The RAA infestation peaks were observed little earlier on apple trees associated with *C. bursa-pastoris* than in the other treatments (late April and early May respectively, Fig. 5A). Over the whole season, we found a significant effect of the plant treatment on the number of RAA colonies, but we did not detect such an effect on the RAA abundance (Table 1). The number of RAA colonies was significantly lower in apple trees associated with *V. sativa* than in apple trees associated with the three other treatments.

Over the whole season, we recorded 239 generalist predators in RAA colonies (hoverfly larvae: 25, ladybug larvae: 6, ladybug adults: 17, earwigs: 177 and spiders: 14) with a peak in mid-May (Fig. 5B). Ants were found in 26.4% ($\pm 9.3\%$) of monitored apple trees. Ant occurrence and generalist predator

abundance were not affected by the plant treatment, but significantly and positively affected by the RAA abundance (Table 1). We recorded on average 1.1 (± 2.7) mummies per tree and sampling date over the whole season but with high discrepancy among apple trees and sampling dates (Fig. 5C). The estimated RAA parasitism rate per tree and sampling date was 4.9% ($\pm 1.4\%$). The plant treatment had a significant effect on the parasitism rate, which also significantly increased with RAA abundances (Table 1). The number of mummies in RAA colonies was 2.7 times higher in apple trees associated with *V. persica* than in control plots. Accordingly, parasitism rate was higher on apple trees associated with *V. persica* than bare soil plots (Fig. 4C). The proportion of RAA distorted apples per tree was very low ranging from 0 to 6%. Plant treatment had no effect on the proportion of distorted apples (Table 1).

Discussion

In this study we compared parasitoid wasp recruitment by three common plant species in apple orchards, *C. bursa-pastoris*, *V. persica*, and *V. sativa*. We collected a greater number of parasitoid wasps in *V. sativa* and *V. persica* plots, regardless floral unit number. These results suggest that the effect of plant treatment on parasitoid wasp abundances cannot be explained by the number of floral units alone. Although the sampling method used may have underestimated their abundances, we also observed higher numbers of arthropods visiting *V. sativa* and *V. persica* plots than *C. bursa-pastoris*. Furthermore, *V. sativa* and *V. persica* plots bloomed earlier than *C. bursa-pastoris* plots, which may have favoured early arthropod recruitment, subsequently affected the seasonal arthropod dynamics on flowers and enhanced host availability for numerous parasitoid taxa. Accordingly, parasitoid wasp communities were different between the three plant species. Ichneumonidae and Pteromalidae were more specialised than other parasitoid families and occurred mainly on *V. persica* and *V. sativa* plots. *Aphidius* was mainly associated with *C. bursa-pastoris* and *V. persica* plots and *Chorebus* was mainly collected on *V. sativa* plots.

First, plant effects on the abundance of parasitoid wasps may be mediated by the quantity of sugar produced by *V. persica* and *V. sativa* flowers, which is higher than the quantity of sugar produced by

C. bursa-pastoris flowers (Baude et al., 2016). Differences in nectar composition between plants, particularly the sucrose/hexose ratio, also need be considered, as parasitoid wasps may prefer sucrose to hexose sugars (Vatalla et al., 2006; Nave et al., 2017). Second, the occurrence of different hosts may also explain the differences in abundance and composition of parasitoid wasp communities between the flowering plant species (Boivin et al., 2012). Accordingly, Zytynska et al., (2021) showed that the diversity of aphids on non-crop plants plays a greater role in the recruitment of natural enemies than the provision of floral resources. Pteromalidae preference for *V. persica* and *V. sativa* plots may be related to the occurrences of primary parasitoids in agreement with the hyperparasitoid character of several species belonging to this family (Cockfield et al., 2011; Dib et al., 2010). Similarly, the preference of *Aphidius* spp. for *V. persica* plots may be related to the occurrence of several other aphid species in addition to RAA.

The parasitism rate of RAA was globally low for all the plant treatments (4.9% in average), but consistent with previous studies (Albert et al., 2017; Dib et al., 2010). The parasitism rate was significantly higher on apple trees associated with *V. persica* compared to control trees. Most of the parasitoids involved in RAA regulation were recorded in *V. persica* plots, but their abundance remained low (9% of all the parasitoid wasps collected on *V. persica*). This may explain the low magnitude of the observed effect. Furthermore, we identified only two individuals belonging to *Ephedrus persicae* on flower patches, although this species is described to be dominant in RAA colonies of European orchards (Bribosia et al., 2005; Dib et al., 2010; Peusens et al., 2006). These results suggest that the three tested plant species have a small or no effect on RAA parasitoid recruitment. More generally, aphid parasitoids may be more adapted to honeydew sugars and thus less dependent on flowers than parasitoids of hosts that do not produce honeydew (Luquet et al., 2021). Accordingly, Goelen et al. (2018) showed that *A. matricariae* consumed preferentially sugars commonly occurring in honeydew. A comparison of the RAA parasitoid diet with the different sugar sources available in apple orchards would be necessary to confirm the role of plants in parasitoid wasp nutrition.

We observed a significantly lower number of RAA colonies in apple trees associated with *V. sativa* compared to the other treatments, but the density of RAA was not affected by the plant treatment. The abundance of predators was mainly explained by the density of aphids in the apple trees, with no significant effect of plant treatment. The most abundant generalist predators observed in RAA colonies were earwigs, which are less dependent on floral resources than other groups of RAA natural enemies such as hoverflies or lacewings (Lu et al. 2014). This may explain the absence of plant treatment effects on the abundance of predators. This absence of effects on major predators may also explain why aphid abundance was not significantly affected by treatment. The distance between flowering plant plots may have been too low to observe effects of the plant treatment on RAA parasitism. The distance was sufficient to observe differences in arthropod visits on flower plots (as in Campbell et al., 2012; Garbuzov & Ratnieks, 2014 or Warzecha et al., 2018 with 1 to 4m between plots), but natural enemies may move to other patches after floral resource consumption without necessarily staying on adjacent apple trees (Heimpel et al., 2019; Miall et al., 2020). Long-term dynamics may also explain the dilution effect observed across the trophic chain, with a positive effect of flowering plant species on parasitoid wasp abundances but no apparent effect on pest suppression and a small effect on RAA parasitism. For example, Krimmer et al. (2021) showed that newly established flowering vegetation (1-2 years old) had a lower effect on parasitism than older ones (5-6 years old).

To conclude, we demonstrated differences between the tested flowering plants in parasitoid abundance and parasitoid community composition. However, the proportion of parasitoid species attacking RAA was relatively small (6 % of the total abundance). Consequently, the differences in RAA parasitism were only significant between the bare soil and the *V. persica* plots, which showed the highest RAA parasitoid abundances. Consequently, detailed identification of parasitoid wasps visiting flowering plant species is needed to assess the recruitment of parasitoid taxa involved in target pest parasitism and thus to better evaluate the efficacy of flowering plant species in promoting pest regulation.

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Table 1. Results of the generalised linear mixed models (GLMM) analysing the effects of flowering plant treatments (including bare soil) in 32 plots observed at five sampling dates. Plant treatment was corrected by two covariates, the abundances of floral units (number/date/plot) or RAA (average tree values/date/plot). Arthropod and parasitoid wasp abundances were recorded at each date in the flower plots. Number of RAA colonies and proportion of RAA distorted apples were recorded on two apple trees associated with these flower plots at the same dates (average tree values/date/plot). RAA and generalist predator abundances, ant occurrence, and RAA parasitism were recorded in RAA colonies of these two apple trees (average tree values/date/plot). χ^2 : chi-square test statistic, df: degrees of freedom, p : p-value. Bold numbers indicate significant p-values ($p < 0.05$).

		Total arthropod abundance	Parasitoid wasp abundance	Number of RAA colonies	RAA abundance	Proportion of RAA distorted apples	Generalist predator abundance	Ant occurrence	RAA parasitism rate
Plant treatment	χ^2	145.89	43.01	13.5	5.97	7.17	2.71	2.34	10.92
	df	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3
	p	<0.001	<0.001	0.004	0.11	0.07	0.44	0.51	0.01
Number of floral units	χ^2	5.32	0.82						
	df	1	1						
	p	0.02	0.37						
	χ^2						5.58	6.93	15.41

RAA abundance	df		1	1	1
	<i>p</i>		0.02	<0.001	<0.001

Figure 1. Experimental design. The three tested plants *Capsella bursa-pastoris*, *Veronica persica* and *Vicia sativa* were intercropped with apple trees in two experimental apple orchards (eight replicate plots per treatment in a randomised block design). Bare soil was used as negative control. Each plot comprised two apple trees framed by $2,5\text{ m}^2$ of one of the tested plants or bare soil. The two orchards were 250 m apart.

Figure 2. Dynamics per sampling date of the number of floral units per m² (A), the total number of arthropods per plot (B) and the abundance of parasitoid wasps per plot for each plant or bare soil treatment (C). Squares represent the mean value per plot and sampling date and bars represent standard errors. GLMM statistics are shown in Table 1.

Figure 3. Comparison of parasitoid communities between three plant treatments. Total number of parasitoid wasps collected for each family and per plant treatment **(A)**. Non-metric multidimensional scaling (NMDS) plots showing divergence in parasitoid communities (at the family level) between the three plant treatments with 95% confidence interval ellipses **(B)**. Total number of Braconidae collected for each genus and each plant treatment; other genera correspond to *Ascogaster*, *Cotesia* and *Orthostigma*, with only one individual per genus **(C)**. Non-metric multidimensional scaling (NMDS) plots showing divergence in Braconidae communities (at the genus level) between the three plant treatments with 95% confidence interval ellipses **(D)**.

Figure 4. Total number of *Aphidius* species per plant treatment **(A)**. Total abundance of parasitoid wasps involved in RAA regulation (sum of *A. matricariae* and *E. persicae*, in black) and total abundance of all other parasitoid species (in grey). Numbers in brackets indicate the observed ratio of RAA parasitoids **(B)**. Model-averaged values (\pm SE) of the effect of plant treatments on RAA parasitism corrected by the number of RAA per tree **(C)**. Bars indicate standard errors. Different letters indicate significant differences between treatments ($p < 0.05$).

Figure 5. Dynamics per sampling date of the average number of RAA per tree **(A)**, average predator abundance per tree **(B)**, and average number of mummies per tree **(C)** per plot for each plant or bare soil treatment. Predators and mummies were counted in all the RAA colonies observed on the two monitored apple trees per plot. Dots represent mean tree values per plot. Squares and bars represent the mean tree values and standard errors for each plant treatment, respectively. Statistics for the GLMM are shown in Table 1.